

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)
Big science

Horticulture and agrofood

Medical Instruments

Create your business in Photonics!

Various
Advanced Manufacturing technologies

Photonics is part of the High Tech Systems & Materials (HTSM) topsector policy of the Dutch Government.

The Photonics R&D agenda has been assigned by the HTSM top team to roadmaps which are an integral part of the Innovation contract of HTSM with the government. The Netherlands has a strong scientific position in important photonics segments and a highly qualified high tech industry that can bring photonics into numerous markets. Dutch internationals like ASML, Philips and OCE/Canon are big players in the photonics area and the Netherlands has also more than 200 SMEs which are already embracing photonics for innovation. A smart photonics ecosystem has been realized covering different important value chains. Finally also the regional government of the south-east of the Netherlands embraced photonics with an own so called Photon Delta Program that is focused on the further industrialization of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs).

Mature photonics technologies

Lasers, lenses, light sources, mirrors and opto-electronic devices are important subsystems of the production machines of wafers for the semiconductor industry in the Netherlands. ASML, the Dutch supplier of production equipment for wafers to produce integrated circuits covers about 80% of the world market. A challenge for ASML is the introduction of a new extreme ultra violet (EUV) light source to be able to produce circuits with smaller nanostructures.

The Dutch Photonics sector also has strong international positions in medical instruments (imaging, detection, diagnostics) and printing (copiers) industries. The main current challenge is to organize the industrialization of all possible value chains for applications that use photonics based technologies.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Advanced Manufacturing technologies

Important challenge : The semiconductor focused ecosystem in the south of the Netherlands wants to come to the industrialization of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs). In PICs functionality is based on the processing of optical signals in different building blocks. It is expected that PICs will follow a similar route that the electronic integrated circuits industry did 20-30 years ago. Important parts of the supply chain already are very active. The challenge is to come to more PICs based applications.

Medical Instruments

Market description : market with a strong growth. All medical systems comprise a combination of photonic components (lasers, detectors, lenses), microelectronics, mechanics and software.

Technologies : Spectroscopy, imaging, advanced microscopy, different other diagnostic systems, therapeutic laser systems.

Trends, challenges : Miniaturization of the systems is often desirable to bring the instruments towards the practitioner/patient..

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

Market description : The ICT market with its applications of TVs, computers and phones continuous to be an important dynamic market and will be driven by IOT, wireless broadband, datacom with new antenna systems based on optical interconnects, and so on.

Technologies : WIFI, LIFI, FTHH, GPON, WDM-PON, ...

Challenge : The main challenges in product development are on-chip integration and miniaturization by using integrated photonics (PICs).

Horticulture and agrofood

Market description : Growth stimulating lighting systems, photonics based sensors for monitoring of climate and growth conditions in greenhouses, photonic trace gas detection for monitoring of crop conditions in the field and in stores, monitoring of soil conditions (fertilization) and salt-fresh water ratios, quality monitoring of packed nutrition and fruit, and so on.

Challenge : The effective and efficient organization of the value chains.

Big science

Market description : Big science programs are becoming more important and have great economic impact. Examples of big science projects where photonics based instruments plays significant roles are CERN, ITER, ESRF, ESS, E-ELT, HFML, ESA and ESO.

Dutch companies are quite active in these networks.

Challenges : Improvement of the interaction between government, researchers and supplying industry; Pushing of technology boundaries.

Various

Market description : Further there are many other market segments where Dutch companies play important roles to develop photonics based applications. Examples of markets are defense & security, earth & environmental observation, industry, and so on.

Examples of product market combinations are OLED, spectroscopy, copiers, solar panel production equipment, sensors, cameras, and so on.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in The Netherlands

- Programs with financial support: In the Netherlands there has been a small decade of financial support for the R&D of photonic devices. This program stops December 2015. More generic national programs for further R&D will stay in the future. Also Horizon 2020 will be used. Finally the regional Photon Delta program with a focus on integrated photonics will start in 2016.
- Networking support: Support comes from the national cluster PhotonicsNL. Further each year there is the national Photonics Event with a meet & match. Company missions are organized to different parts of the world. Also a network is discussing about the start of the Dutch Optical Centre (DOC) in 2016. The DOC is planned to be product oriented.
- Contact & Information: René de Groot - E-mail: rene.de.groot@kvk.nl

Photonics4All is a European Horizon 2020 Outreach project, funded by the European Commission to promote photonics and light based technologies to young people, entrepreneurs and the general public across the EU. Photonics4all's unique selling point is that it will both develop a set of new promotional tools and apply them during a wide variety of outreach activities with different audiences.

*Discover our unique approach and check out our tools and events :
<http://photonics4all.eu/>*

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light